

Green synthesis and catalytic activity of composite NiO-Ag nanoparticles for photocatalytic degradation of dyes

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Abstract : Preparation of composite NiO-Ag and its individual monometallic nanoparticles is demonstrated by utilizing non-toxic and abundantly available tannic acid at room temperature through an eco-friendly green aqueous technique. These monometallic and composite nanoparticles were characterized using TEM, SAED, EDAX, photoluminences, Zeta potential, IR and UV-Vis spectroscopy. Monometallic and composite nanoparticles have a narrow size distribution with spherical morphology. Moreover, the average diameters of all these three different nanoparticles are almost identical and ranges from 7 nm to 10 nm as measured from HRTEM. Comparative catalytic efficacy of the nanoparticulate materials were studied employing photo degradation of a cationic (methyl violet) and anionic (methyl orange) dye at room temperature. NiO-Ag composite nanoparticles exhibits higher catalytic potential and the rate constants for photo degradation reactions follow the order of the reaction condition : $k_{\text{NiO-Ag composite NPs}} > k_{\text{NiO NPs}} > k_{\text{Ag NPs}} > k_{\text{uncat}}$. Higher catalytic performance of the composite system is attributed to the composition effect which basically results due to synergistic electronic effect.

Keywords : Composite nanoparticles, green aqueous synthesis, methyl violet, methyl orange, nanocatalyst, synergistic effect.

Introduction

Composite bimetallic nanostructures have been fabricated because of their wide range of applications in controlling energy of plasmon absorption band, electrochemical, magnetic, catalytic and biomedical applications, tuneable optical behaviour and play a crucial role in biosensing¹⁻³. Bimetallic nanomaterials of various size and morphology are synthesized using various techniques like vapour deposition, ionic liquid, micro emulsions, electrochemical method, solvothermal reduction, thermal decomposition of organic complexes, radiolytic reduction, environmental benign methods, alcohol reduction etc.⁴⁻¹¹. In spite of the fact that there are various routes for the fabrication of composite bimetallic nanoparticles of different morphologies, green approaches have drawn must attention, owing to the growing need for development of eco-friendly environmentally technologies, its high atom economy, less time consumption, simplicity for the experimental procedures, versatility etc. Several biosynthesis routes of nanoscopic particles were developed using

plants (leaves, roots, stems etc.), plant products and microorganism, which is a huge contribution to the progress of development for green synthesis¹²⁻¹⁴. Although preparation of bimetallic NPs employing various techniques have gained maturity, still there is a need to envisage a novel, facile route of tailoring bimetallic nanostructure of different compositions utilizing nontoxic, biocompatible and abundantly available resources.

In this work, we have demonstrated a simple, biocompatible green approach for the preparation of NiO, Ag monometallic and composite NiO-Ag NPs of alloy type utilizing tannic acid (TA) in alkaline medium at room temperature. Water was used as green solvent throughout the synthesis procedure. TA served a dual purpose by acting both as an excellent reducing and capping agent. The aforementioned particles are remarkably stable. The fabricated composite system displayed significant catalytic behaviour during photo degradation of dye; methyl violet (MV) and methyl orange (MO) was used as a model dye. Synergistic electronic effect due to composition of

the composite nanocatalyst preponderantly plays a typical part during the degradation of the dye. Dyes are one of the major environmental issues and should be treated well before discharging in the environment. Nanoparticles/nanotechnology might be a solution of such environmental issues¹⁵⁻¹⁷.

Materials and experiment details

Materials :

All the chemicals were of AR grade. Silver nitrate (AgNO_3) and nickel nitrate hexahydrate $\text{Ni}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ were purchased from Merck Pvt. Ltd. While, tannic acid (TA), methyl orange (MO) and methyl violet 10B (MV) were obtained Himedia Laboratories Pvt. Ltd. NaOH was procured from Merck Pvt. Ltd. and their solutions were prepared in double distilled water (DDW).

Synthesis of NiO, Ag monometallic and composite NiO-Ag NPs :

0.005 M of $\text{Ni}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and AgNO_3 solutions in DDW were prepared by weighing out the required amount of salts in 10 ml of DDW respectively. The fabrication of monometallic NPs was accomplished by taking 1.6 ml of 0.05 M TA in 10 ml of each metal salt solution and 400 μL of 0.02 M NaOH solution to established an alkaline pH of the reaction mixture. This reaction mixture was stirred uniformly for 2 h at room temperature and the whole reaction mixture was leave undisturbed for one night. The generation of NiO-Ag composite nanoscale particles was performed by maintaining the same reaction condition and procedure except instead of 10 ml of salt solution; 5 ml each of Ni and Ag salt solutions (0.005 M) were taken. The pH of the reaction system was also maintained by employing 0.02 M NaOH solution.

Catalytic activity of the synthesized nanoparticles :

Photo catalytic reduction of MV in aqueous medium was monitored with the help of UV-Vis spectrophotometer at $\lambda_{\text{max}} = 584 \text{ nm}$, a prominent characteristic peak of MV. To 10 μL of $1 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$ MV, 20 μL of M NPs (i.e. NiO, Ag monometallic and composite NiO-Ag NPs) were added separately in a 3.5 ml of quartz cuvette. The total volume for the chemical degradation reaction system was fixed at 3 ml by adding DDW. The progress of the reaction was monitored by noting the fall in absorbance at 584 nm due to MV at room temperature. Similar procedure

was also repeated for the uncatalysed reaction. Instead of introducing metallic nanoscaled particles, 10 μL of DDW was added in order to maintain a consistent total volume of the reaction system.

A comparative study for photo catalytic degradation of MO was also performed spectrophotometrically at the characteristic maximum wavelength of MO i.e. 461 nm. The reaction was monitored by taking 10 μL of $1 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$ MV and 20 μL of synthesized NPs each of the aforementioned NPs at natural pH medium. The total volume of the reaction mixture was also maintained at 3 ml by adjusting with 2970 μL of DDW. Photocatalytic degradation of MO was also carried out in the absence of nanocatalyst by fixing the total volume of the reaction mixture at 3 ml with DDW. All the kinetic studies reported in this work were carried out at an ambient temperature of 25 °C.

Characterizations of the synthesized nanoscopic particles :

Ultraviolet visible (UV-Vis) spectroscopy :

All UV-Vis spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer Lambda 35 UV-Vis spectrophotometer fitted with Petlier system. The absorption spectra of the prepared NPs were recorded by taking the aqueous dispersion of the NPs and scanned in the range of 200–800 nm at room temperature.

Energy dispersive X-ray (EDAX) analysis :

EDAX data of the so-synthesized NPs were obtained by employing SEI quanta 250 model of SEM instrument. An adequate amount of dried powder NiO, Ag monometallic and composite NiO-Ag NPs were used for the measurement.

Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) and selected area electron diffraction (SAED) :

TEM and SAED micrographs of the particles were taken with JEM-2100 transmission electron microscope operating at 60-200 KV STEPS. A drop of dilute aqueous dispersion of the NiO, Ag and composite NiO-Ag NPs were put on carbon coated copper grids and the grids were dried at room temperature. After complete drying of the grids, TEM and SAED patterns of the particles were taken.

X-Ray diffraction (XRD) analysis :

X-Ray diffraction patterns of the samples were taken

by Philips XRD instrument; properly dried powder samples were utilized to carry out the diffraction experiment. After preparation, the samples were washed effectively with DDW and finally with ethanol. The samples were then allowed to dry at room temperature.

Photoluminences (PL) :

The emission behaviours of the mono and composite NPs dispersed in water were carried out by photoluminescence (PL) spectrophotometer, F-7000 fluorescence spectrophotometer from Hitachi, with Xe-lamp by irradiating the fabricated monometallic and composite NPs at different exciting wavelength.

Zeta potential (ζ) :

To measure surface charge, sample preparation has to be carried out very carefully as this measurement is very sensitive to foreign particles like dusts. Sample was prepared by diluting the required amount of sample in double distilled water and sonicated for 1–2 min. A minimum of 10 mm of sample solution was taken and put in a glass or plastic cuvette. This cuvette is placed in the cell holder and scanned in range of 1 to 100 nm at room temperature. All the charge measurement in this work has been carried out using Zetasizer Nano ZS90 of Malvern Instruments Ltd. of National Institute of Technology, Manipur.

Fourier transformed-infra red (FTIR) spectroscopy :

Perkin-Elmer Spectrum-2 spectrophotometry instrument was utilized to measure FT-IR spectra of TA and the so-synthesized NPs. The particles after fabrication were washed thoroughly, collected and then finally redispersed in DDW. Liquid FT-IR spectra of TA and the synthesized NiO, Ag monometallic and composite NiO-Ag NPs were recorded in the range 400 to 4000 cm^{-1} . The transmission of the solvent, water was finally omitted from the readings of the samples recorded.

Results and discussion

Composite NiO-Ag NPs, NiO and Ag monometallic NPs were synthesized successfully by utilizing TA in alkaline medium; the formation of composite NiO-Ag particles was accomplished by co-reduction of Ni^{2+} to Ni^0 and Ag^{1+} to Ag^0 at room temperature. The formation of nanoscale NiO, Ag and NiO-Ag particles is directly confirmed by UV-Vis spectroscopy. Fig. 1 displays the UV-Vis spectra of NiO and Ag monometallic NPs with dis-

Fig. 1. UV-Vis spectra of NiO-Ag, Ag and NiO NPs.

tinct surface plasmon resonance (SPR) bands at 330 nm and 422 nm respectively^{18–21}. On other hand, composite NiO-Ag NPs exhibit SPR band at 407 nm as presented in Fig. 1, this sudden disappearance of the characteristic peaks of individual components of the composite system along with shifting of peak indicates that the composite system is not just a physical mixture of the constituent metals^{22–25}. Physical mixture of two metals in a solution is expected to show two SPR bands where as an alloy/core shell shows a single plasmon resonance band^{26,27}. However, from the UV-Vis spectra alone it is difficult to conclude whether the composite system is an alloy or of core shell in nature.

The size and morphology of these mono and composite NPs were studied by using transmission electron microscopic technique. Fig. 2 shows TEM and SAED images of NiO, Ag monometallic and NiO-Ag NPs. The prepared particles are spherical in shape with an average diameter ranging from 7 nm to 10 nm in both mono and composite system as estimated via HRTEM [Fig. 2(i)]. The SAED patterns of the synthesized NPs indicates crystalline behaviour of the tailored nanoscale particles and are presented in Fig. 2(ii).

EDAX provides elemental information regarding the constituents of multi-components metallic system. The inclusion of metallic Ni and Ag in EDAX pattern reflects the bimetallic nature of NiO-Ag composite NPs. The individual metals, Ni and Ag, are present almost in the ratio of 1 : 2 (weight ratio) within the composite bimetallic system. EDAX results rule out the presence of C and Na in the prepared particles, author believes that this elements come from the tannic acid and NaOH.

Fig. 2. (i) TEM and (ii) SAED micrographs of (a) NiO-Ag, (b) Ag and (c) NiO NPs.

XRD patterns of the fabricated NiO-Ag, Ag and NiO NPs are shown in Fig. 3, further substantiate their crystalline nature. NiO NPs shows diffraction peaks at $2\theta = 37^\circ$, 44.3° and 53° which may be indexed to (111) and (200) planes of FCC crystal structure as displayed in Fig. 4(a)^{28,29}. On the contrary, Ag NPs exhibit three characteristic obvious peaks at $2\theta = 38.7^\circ$, 47.5° and 65.8° corresponding to (111), (200) and (220) FCC crystal planes as displayed in Fig. 3(b)^{30,31}. Fig. 3(c) displays XRD pattern of the composite bimetallic system showing sharp peaks at $2\theta = 38.12^\circ$, 44.35° and 64.6° . In the composite system, the characteristic peaks of NiO and Ag are absent instead their peaks got shifted. This result further supports the fact that composite NiO-Ag NPs is an alloy not a core shell or a physical mixture of individual metals³².

Luminences spectra of composite and mono metallic system are given in Fig. 4. When Ag NPs is excited at 422 nm emission is obtain at 566 nm. On exciting NiO at 330 nm it shows emission at 477 nm and composite system shows emission spectra at 461 nm when excited at 407 nm. PL emission is mainly due to the recombination

Fig. 3. XRD patterns of (a) Ag, (b) NiO and (c) NiO-Ag NPs.

Fig. 4. Luminences spectra of NiO-Ag, NiO and Ag NPs.

of generated holes and excited electrons in the particles^{33,34}. This blue shift in emission spectrum of NiO-Ag NPs with respect to its individual monometallic NPs indicates the presence of interstitial oxygen in the crystal structure. Ghazaleh *et al.* have reported similar finding when NiO is doped with Mg³⁵. Author strongly believe that presence of interstitial oxygen in crystal system of NiO-Ag NPs may result in modification of its surface.

On other hand, the stability of the particles is characterized by measuring the Zeta potential of the particles in the dispersion as presented in Fig. 5. Particles seem to be very stable as its Zeta potential is high then ± 25 mV³⁶.

Fig. 5. Zeta potential of (a) Ag, (b) NiO and (c) NiO-Ag NPs.

Zeta potential of Ag NPs is -41.6 mV that of NiO NPs is -42.4 mV and composite NPs is of -42.6 mV.

Fig. 6 show FT-IR spectra of the synthesized NPs and TA. In the spectra the broad peak of OH radical (group) (3400 cm^{-1}) were shrunken (narrow) and it is almost reduced in case of metallic NPs indicating that the hydroxyl

Fig. 6. IR spectra of (a) tannic acid, (b) Ag NPs, (c) NiO NPs and (d) NiO-Ag NPs.

groups of TA are utilized in reduction of metal ions and stabilising the particles. Bands at 1490 cm^{-1} and 1300 cm^{-1} correspond to aromatic C=C and phenolic C-O stretching vibrations from which it can be concluded that majority of TA is present in its oxidised form³⁷. IR spectra indicate that TA is well coated over NiO, Ag and composite NiO-Ag NPs hereby acting both as reducing as

well as capping agent. Both the monometallic and composite NPs exhibit excellent stability as we observed that particles remained un-settle for more than eight months. Thus, it be anticipated that identical size and morphology of the prepared NPs might be due to similarly reaction conditions and effective capping capability of TA. The possible mechanism for the formation of NPs through reduction of metal salts by TA is given below in Scheme 1³⁸.

Scheme 1. Probable reaction mechanism for the formation of NPs.

As such fabricated monometallic and composite NPs were used as nanocatalysts in photocatalytic reduction of MV and MO at room temperature in natural pH medium (6.4). MV shows absorbance peak at 584 nm and while MO show at 461 nm . Decrease in these corresponding absorbance peak indicates the reduction/degradation of dye. Uncatalysed and catalysed photocatalytic reduction of MV by NPs is given in Fig. 7. The photocatalytic degradation of MV follows first order kinetics and the rate constants determined from the plot of $\log A$ vs time given in Fig. 8(a) are also listed in Table 1(i). Composite NiO-Ag NPs able to reduced 71.4% of MV in 140 min while NiO and Ag NPs reduced 60% and 40% of MV in 140 min respectively. The rate of degradation of MV is maximum for composite NiO-Ag NPs followed by NiO and Ag NPs. Rate constant calculated for degradation process follows the order : $k_{\text{NiO-Ag NPs}} > k_{\text{NiO NPs}} > k_{\text{Ag NPs}} > k_{\text{uncat}}$ at room temperature.

IR spectra of MV composed of bands at 2921 cm^{-1} and 2856 cm^{-1} which are of asymmetric and symmetric stretching of C-H, bands at 1589 cm^{-1} and 1473 cm^{-1} can be attributed to C=C stretching, band at 1583 cm^{-1} is of N-H bending, bands in range of 1476 cm^{-1} , 1240 cm^{-1} and 1015 cm^{-1} can be attributed to C-H, C=O and C-O stretch vibrations³⁹. Significant changes in the spectra of MV is observed after treating with NPs as given in the

Fig. 7. Photoreduction of MV dye (a) uncatalysed, catalysed by (b) Ag NPs, (c) NiO NPs and (d) NiO-Ag NPs.

Fig. 8. (a) Kinetics studies of uncatalysed and catalysed photo reduction of MV and (b) IR spectra of (i) MV, (ii) MV treated with Ag, (iii) MV treated with Ag and (iv) MV treated with NiO-Ag NPs.

Table 1. Calculated rate constants for the photo catalytic degradation of (i) methyl violet and (ii) methyl orange at room temperature

Sl. No.	Type of NP	Rate constants (in min^{-1}) for photo degradation of MV at room temperature (i)	Rate constants (in min^{-1}) for photo degradation of MO at room temperature (ii)
1.	Uncatalyzed	2.7×10^{-4}	–
2.	Ag	1×10^{-3}	1.168×10^{-4}
3.	NiO	2.4×10^{-3}	1.235×10^{-4}
4.	NiO-Ag	8.1×10^{-3}	3×10^{-3}

spectra Fig. 8(b). Most of the band where shifted indicating the strong interaction of NPs with MV and formation of a new compound different from original substrate⁴⁰. Possible mechanism for the reduction of MV is given in Scheme 2.

Both uncatalysed and catalysed photo degradation of MO by fabricated NPs is given in Fig. 9. Photoreduction of MO is less significant as compared with MV, the reduction process is very slow and almost negligible in case of Fig. 9(b and c). Fabricated NPs is relatively unreactive towards MO over time scales of hours. NiO-Ag NPs able to reduced only 40% of MO in 15 h while NiO and Ag reduced 23% and 15% of MO in 15 h. Possible reason of

Scheme 2. Possible mechanism for the reduction of methyl violet using NPs.

Fig. 9. Photocatalytic degradation of MO at room temperature (a) uncatalysed, catalysed by (b) Ag NPs, (c) NiO NPs and (d) NiO-Ag NPs.

this finding can be attributed to the nature of charge of particles and dye. MO is an anionic dye and on dissolving in water MO give its anionic form as given below^{41,42}.

As determined from zeta potential, the potential difference existing between the surface of NPs and bulk liquid is negative. So the negatively charge MO cannot interact strongly with the surface of the NPs and it interrupts in transfer of electrons between MO and NPs. Because of this reason the reductive photo degradation of MO is not supported by the fabricated NPs. On other hand, MV is a cationic dye so it strongly interact with NPs and can absorb on the surface of NPs which result in effective transfer of electrons between the two systems. So degradation rate of MV by fabricated NPs is high and effective.

Photocatalytic degradation of dyes in aqueous medium involves generation of electron (e^-) and hole (h^+) pair

leading to the formation of hydroperoxyl radicals, superoxide radicals anions and hydroxyl radicals. These radicals act as oxidising species in photooxidation of dye by scavenging the electrons in conduction band which indirectly prevent the recombination of e^- and h^+ . Electron in the conduction band can be utilized by dye molecules to generate dye radicals anions and leading to the degradation of dye⁴³. The possible mechanism for the degradation of dye can be explained as given below^{44,45}.

In the photo degradation of MV and MO the higher catalytic efficacy of composite NPs over the monometallic NPs is confirmed. Such dominating catalytic behaviour of composite NPs in the reactions may be attributed to synergistic effect with arises due to uneven distribution of electrons. Basically, this synergistic electronic effect is contributes from composition effect of multicomponent system. The electronic interaction between different components may lead to significant modification of the electronic structure of NPs, which leads to an enhancement of catalytic activity⁴⁶. Author believes that greater photocatalytic efficacy of NiO NPs than Ag NPs may be accounted to the small energy gap of NiO NPs as compared to Ag NPs. The optical band gaps (E_g) for the different nanocatalyst were calculated using the Tauc relation,

$$\alpha h\nu = B(h\nu - E_g)^n \quad (1)$$

where α is the absorption coefficient, B is a constant, $h\nu$ is the energy of the photons and exponent ' n ' depends on the type of the transition and ' n ' may have values 1/2, 2, 3/2 or 3 corresponding to allowed direct, allowed indirect, forbidden direct or forbidden indirect transitions respectively^{47,48}. α and transmittance (T) are correlated as

$$T = \exp(-\alpha L) \quad (2)$$

$\alpha = -(\ln T)/L$, where, L is thickness of the sample.

For allowed direct transition $n = 1/2$ so,

$$(h\nu \ln T)^2 = B^2 L^2 (h\nu - E_g) \quad (3)$$

The exact value of the optical band gap can be obtained by extrapolating the straight-line portion of $(h\nu \ln T)^2$ vs $h\nu$ graph to the $h\nu$ axis (shown in Fig. 10). Optical band gap thus calculated for NiO, Ag and NiO-Ag NPs are 4.9 eV, 5 eV and 4.4 eV respectively. Band gap of bulk nickel is 4 eV that of bulk Ag is zero eV and 2.6 eV in Ag dimer nanoparticles⁴⁹. The increase in the band gap of NiO and Ag NPs with decrease in the particle size may be due to the quantum confinement effect. As the size of the crystal continues to decrease, so the number of the orbital energy levels decrease and the band gap increases⁵⁰. Band gap of the composite NiO-Ag NPs is small as compared to individual monometallic NPs. Such narrowing of band gap by introducing another metal to the host is also reported before by Ahmed *et al.* and Sankara Reddy *et.al.*^{51,52}. Our work have directed a rational way to design composite NiO-Ag NPs via an environmental friendly approach using TA and facilitates in the study of composition effect on nanocatalysis.

Conclusion

Using environmental friendly method monometallic and composite system of NiO and Ag NPs were fabricated at room temperature. The synthesized nanodimensional particles were stable for more than eight months in aqueous medium. Co-reduction of Ni and Ag metal salt solutions by TA enables successfully in the formation of alloy particles having excellent catalytic efficiency as compared to monometallic particles. Photo degradation of MV dye was studied using the synthesized NPs and rate constants cal-

Fig. 10. Plot of $(hv \ln T)^2$ against hv for determination of band gaps of (a) Ag NPs, (b) NiO NPs and (c) NiO-Ag bimetallic NPs.

culated from the plot of $\log A$ vs time reveals that composite NiO-Ag NPs possess greater catalytic potential as compared to its constituent monometallic particles. Photo degradation of MO is also documented even though it is less significant. As fabricated NPs is not effective towards the degradation of anionic dye in natural pH. The rate constant in both the degradation reactions follow the order : $k_{\text{NiO-Ag NPs}} > k_{\text{NiO NPs}} > k_{\text{Ag NPs}}$ at room temperature. Introduction of a second component to a metal system results in the alternation of electronic property of the composite system hereby enhancing catalytic property of the bimetallic or composite system as compared with individual metal particles. This finding is strongly supported by the result obtained from luminences spectra and band or energy gap calculated.

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References

1. P. R. Reddy, K. Mohana Raju and N. S. Reddy, *Chem. Sci. Rev. Lett.*, 2013, **1**, 228.
2. M. Valodkar, S. Modi, A. Pal and S. Thakore, *Mat. Res. Bull.*, 2011, **46**, 384.
3. F. Tao, *Chem. Soc. Rev.*, 2012, **41**, 7977.
4. G. Ferk, J. Stergar, D. Makovec, A. Hamler, Z. Jaglicic, M. Drofenik and I. Ban, *J. Alloys Compd.*, 2015, **648**, 53.
5. S. Senapati, A. Ahmad, M. I. Khan, M. Sastry and R. Kumar, *Small.*, 2005, **1**, 517.
6. K. Quester, M. A. Borja and E. C. Longoria, *Micron.*, 2013, **54**, 1.
7. M. Cai, R. Xiao, T. Yan and H. Zhao, *J. Organomet. Chem.*, 2014, **749**, 55.
8. S. H. Wu and D. H. Chen, *J. Colloid Interface Sci.*, 2003, **259**, 282.
9. D. Maity, M. M. R. Mollick, D. Mondal, B. Bhowmick, S.

- K. Neogi, A. Banerjee, S. Chattopadhyay, S. Banbyopadhyay and D. Chattopadhyay, *Carbohydrpolym.*, 2013, **98**, 80.
10. T. C. R. Rocha and D. Zanchet, *J. Phys. Chem. (C)*, 2007, **111**, 6989.
 11. G. Q. Lui, W. P. Cai and C. H. Liang, *Cryst. Growth Des.*, 2008, **8**, 2748.
 12. X. H. Li, J. Wang, Y. X. Zhang, M. Q. Li and J. H. Liu, *Eur. J. Inorg. Chem.*, 2010, **5**, 1806.
 13. C. C. Wu and D. H. Chen, *Gold Bulletin*, 2010, **43**, 234.
 14. N. A. Raouf, N. M. A. Enazi and I. B. M. Ibraheem, *J. Arabjc.*, 2013, in press (doi:10.1016/j.arabjc.2013.11.044).
 15. V. K. Gupta, R. Jain, A. Mittal, T. A. Saleh, A. Nayak, S. Agarwal and S. Sikarwar, *Mat. Sci. Eng. (C)*, 2012, **32**, 12.
 16. A. Mittal, J. Mittal, A. Malviya, D. Kaur and V. K. Gupta, *J. Colloid Interface Sci.*, 2010, **342**, 518.
 17. A. Mittal, D. Kaur, A. Malviya, J. Mittal and V. K. Gupta, *J. Colloid Interface Sci.*, 2009, **337**, 345.
 18. S. Chandra, A. Kumar and P. K. Tomar, *J. Saudi Chem. Soc.*, 2014, **18**, 437.
 19. A. M. Meftah, E. Saion, M. M. B. A. Moxsin and H. B. Zainuddin, *JSS*, 2009, **17**, 167.
 20. D. Li and S. Komarneni, *J. Am. Ceram Soc.*, 2006, **89**, 1510.
 21. A. Dutta and S. K. Dolui, *Applied Surface Science*, 2011, **257**, 6889.
 22. B. Xia, F. He and L. Li, *Langmuir*, 2013, **29**, 4901.
 23. M. L. Wu, D. L. Chen and T. C. Huang, *Chem. Mater.*, 2001, **13**, 599.
 24. N. Toshima and T. Yonezawa, *New J. Chem.*, 1998, 1179.
 25. D. Lahiri, B. Bunker, B. Mishra, Z. Zhang, D. Maisel, C. M. Doudna, M. F. Bertino, F. D. Blum, A. T. Tokuhira, S. Chattopadhyay, T. Shibata and J. Terry, *J. Appl. Phys.*, 2005, **97**, 094304.
 26. B. W. Boote, H. Byun and J. H. Kim, *Gold Bulletin*, 2013, **46**, 185.
 27. H. P. Singh, N. Gupta, S. K. Sharma and R. K. Sharma, *Colloids Surf. A : Physicochemical and Engineering Aspects*, 2013, **416**, 43.
 28. N. Dharmaraj, P. Prabu, S. Nagarajan, C. H. Kim, J. H. Park and H. Y. Kim, *Mat. Sci. Eng. (B)*, 2006, **128**, 111.
 29. J. Park, E. Kang, S. U. Son, H. M. Park, M. K. Lee, J. Kim, K. W. Kim, H. J. Noh, J. H. Park, C. J. Bae, J. G. Park and T. Hyeon, *Adv. Mater.*, 2005, **4**, 429.
 30. M. K. Swamy, K. M. Sudipta, K. Jayanta and S. Balasubramanya, *Appl. Nanosci.*, 2015, **5**, 73.
 31. X. Yang, W. He, S. Wang, G. Zhou and Y. Tang, *J. Experimental Nanosci.*, 2014, **9**, 541.
 32. K. Kim, K. L. Lim and K. S. Shin, *J. Phys. Chem. (C)*, 2011, **115**, 14844.
 33. P. Qu, J. Zhao, T. Shen and H. Hidaka, *J. Mol. Catal. A : Chem.*, 1998, **129**, 257.
 34. D. Zhang, M. Wen, S. Zhang, P. Liu, W. Zhu, G. Li and H. Li, *Appl. Catal. B : Environmental*, 2014, **147**, 610.
 35. (a) A. Ghazaleh, A. Payam and M. T. Siti, *AIP Advances*, 2015, **5**, 077161; (b) D. Sreetama and N. G. Bichitra, *Journal of Nanobiotechnology*, 2012, **10**, 29.
 36. A. D. Mc Naught and A. Wilkinson, "Compendium of Chemical Terminology", Goldbook Blackwell Scientific Publications, Oxford, 1997.
 37. E. Bulut and M. Ozacar, *Ind. Eng. Chem. Res.*, 2009, **48**, 5686.
 38. Z. Yi, X. Li, X. Xu, B. Luo, J. Luo, W. Wu, Y. Yi and Y. Tang, *Colloids Surf. A : Physicochemical*.
 39. D. L. Pavia, G. M. Lampman, G. S. Kriz and J. A. Vyvyan, "Introduction to spectroscopy", Cengage Learning, 2015, 15.
 40. L. Gan, Y. Cheng, T. Palanisami, Z. Chen, M. Megharaj and R. Naidu, *Environ Sci. Pollut. Res.*, 2014, **21**, 10339.
 41. T. K. Saha, N. C. Bhoumik, S. Karmaker, M. G. Ahmed, H. Ichikawa and Y. Fukumori, *J. Water Resource and Protection*, 2010, **2**, 898.
 42. O. A. Attallah, M. A. Al-Ghobashy, M. Nebsen and M. Y. Salem, *RSC Adv.*, 2016, **6**, 11461.
 43. M. R. Hoffman, S. T. Martin, W. Choi and W. Bahnmann, *Chem. Rev.*, 1995, **95**, 69.
 44. A. Houas, H. Lachheb, M. Ksibi, E. Elaloui, C. Guillard and J. M. Herrmann, *Appl. Catal. B : Environmetal*, 2001, **31**, 145.
 45. R. Ameta, D. Kumar and P. Jhalora, *Acta Chim. & Pharm. Indica*, 2014, **4**, 20.
 46. A. K. Singh and Q. Xu, *Chemcatchem.*, 2013, **5**, 652.
 47. M. Dehbashi and M. Aliahmad, *Int. J. Phys. Sci.*, 2012, **7**, 5415.
 48. S. Chakrabarty and K. Chatterjee, *J. Phys. Sci.*, 2009, **13**, 245.
 49. (a) H. Kumar and R. Rani, *International Journal of Engineering and Innovative Technology*, 2013, **3**, 344; (b) V. V. Volkov, Z. L. Wang and B. S. Zou, *Chemical Physics Letters*, 2001, **377**, 117.
 50. L. E. Smart and E. A. Moore, "Sold Sate Chemsitry, An Introduction", Chap. 11, 'Nanoscience', 3rd ed., Taylor and Francis CRC Press, Boca Raton, 2005, 359.
 51. A. S. Ahmed, S. M. Muhamed, M. L. Singla, S. Tabassum, A. H. Naqvi and A. Azam, *J. Luminescence*, 2011, **131**, 1.
 52. R. B. Sankara, R. S. Venkatramana, R. N. Koteeswara and K. J. Pramoda, *Res. J. Material Sci.*, 2013, **1**, 11.

